

The Bhagavad Gita and Indigenous Pedagogy: Re-Envisioning Education Through Indian Knowledge Systems

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Abstract

The Bhagavad Gita is a sacred and revered text which is not just religious in nature but a philosophical and educational guide to our scholars and policy makers. This paper explores Bhagavad Gita as foundational source of indigenous pedagogy within the framework of Indian Knowledge System. It emphasises on Guru-Shishya dialogue stressing on the importance of teacher-student relationship which is necessary for educational journey of an individual. It promotes education as a holistic process combining knowledge (*jnana*), action (*karma*) and devotion (*bhakti*) to achieve self-realisation and ethical living. It mentions principles like experiential learning, community wisdom which are key aspects of contemporary education model. Karma Yoga is learning through action which prepares a student to apply supreme knowledge as knowledge without action is incomplete. The analysis identifies some challenges in implementing Gita-based pedagogy and to address these issues this study proposes context-centric approach.

Bhagavad Gita is the source of inspiration in applying indigenous pedagogy in contemporary times. It lays out roadmap for formulation of educational policies. Gita's principles in the area of education are put into practice in the form of NEP 2020 which integrates Bhagavad Gita as part of Indian Knowledge Systems to promote value-based education, moral integrity and holistic development of individuals. By incorporating Bhagavad Gita into education, we can promote preservation and promotion of our ancient knowledge systems in 21st century world.

Keywords: Knowledge (*jnana*), learner-centred, holistic development, indigenous pedagogy, philosophy into practice, NEP 2020.

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Introduction

Bhagavad Gita is a holy text respected by people around the world for its spiritual philosophy and teachings. It is a section under Mahabharata where Lord Krishna preached Arjuna about one's duty, *karma* when Arjuna was overwhelmed by emotions due to the events surrounding him before Kurukshetra War. These teachings serve as the foundation stone for our morals, ethics in our life. It guides us how to live according to *dharma*, follow ethical principles in conduct of our relations, and most importantly in stressful times when we need a philosopher, friend, advisor, to lead us to the peaceful conclusion. It is more than just being a religious text as it is a fountain of spiritual and ethical Indian philosophy. Gita is highly revered by all the religions as it crosses the religious line and takes us to the other world where religious principles start blurring. It is written in a dialogic form between Lord Krishna and Arjuna. It tells us the path to *Moksha* (liberation) through *bhakti* (devotion) and towards the union of God and *atman* (soul). It talks about various events like duty (*dharma*), action (*Karma Yoga*), knowledge (*Jnana Yoga*). The question arises how knowledge and education are related to Bhagavad Gita. Lord Krishna preached Arjuna about knowledge being the most important element in an individual's life. It makes us understand the importance of knowledge as it makes an individual more ready for it to apply in any situation needed.

Indigenous pedagogy finds its roots in the Bhagavad Gita. It clearly states the purpose, direction, objectives of gaining education.

In contemporary times, the education model faces various challenges which hinders the complete application of education principles and models. These challenges have led us to think of better ways to implement the values and philosophies. Indian Knowledge System comes into the picture and provides insights of ancient knowledge systems and their benefits and application. Bhagavad Gita gives us the ideas which are necessary in today's world for better quality of education.

This paper explores the deep relationship between knowledge, indigenous pedagogy, Bhagavad Gita and their relation in the latest reform in education policy, i.e. NEP 2020. By analysing Gita's wisdom, this paper tries to enforce the reforms needed in contemporary education model. It gives suggestion and way forward in making the educational level of India a top quality one.

Literature Review

Bhagavad Gita is a text which has been extensively researched and has a wide scholarly resource material which acts as assistance for further research in the direction of particularly, education and pedagogy. It will help us to move forward in the direction of research and give us the gaps which are needed to be worked on.

The first question arises why to combine Bhagavad Gita with indigenous pedagogy and Indian Knowledge System. Gita offers a universal philosophy of education and self-development which is relevant beyond religious boundaries. Education should cultivate wisdom, balance, and ethical responsibility, not just intellect. Gita is a philosophical foundation for value-based and holistic education. (Radhakrishnan, 1948)

Ancient Indian education system were student-centred, residential (*gurukul*), value-oriented. Knowledge transmission was closely tied to ethical living and social duty. It offers historical evidence of indigenous pedagogical practices in India. (Altekar, 1934). Indian education is rooted in spiritual, moral, and experiential learning, unlike purely materialist models. True education aims at character formation and self-realisation. Provides a philosophical framework for understanding indigenous Indian pedagogy. (Radhakrishnan, 1927)

Education in Indian thought integrates, knowledge (*jnana*), action (*karma*), devotion (*bhakti*). Learning is a transformative inner journey, not information transfer. Indian metaphysics is directly connected with educational philosophy. (Dasgupta, 1922) The Gita functions as a practical guide for disciplined learning and self-control. Emphasises mindfulness, concentration and self-regulation – key educational skills. (Easwaran, 1993)

Karma Yoga is the central philosophy of Gita. Knowledge must culminate in socially responsible action, not renunciation. Gita is interpreted as practical philosophy of action, highly relevant to education and pedagogy. (Tilak, 1915) Bhagavad Gita is not a sectarian religious text, but a universal spiritual and psychological guide. Learning is not escape from life, but preparation for conscious action in life. Learning should be experiential, activity-based, interest-driven and rejects mechanical rote learning. (Aurobindo, 1922)

Objectives of Study

1. To examine the educational philosophy embedded in Bhagavad Gita through Indian Knowledge Systems.
2. To analyse Bhagavad Gita as source of indigenous pedagogical principles based on Guru-Shishya tradition.
3. To explore key concepts like Karma Yoga, knowledge as elements of pedagogy.
4. To analyse dialogic learner-centred model reflected in Krishna-Arjuna dialogue.

Research Methodology

The study adopts qualitative and interpretative research methodology rooted in textual analysis. Given the nature of Bhagavad Gita, the paper primarily relies on secondary sources and textual interpretation rather than quantitative methods. The Gita is analysed with particular emphasis on education vision and teaching-learning principles. The study employs a hermeneutic approach to interpret key terms and verses such as *karma yoga*, *jnana*, *bhakti*, and *dharma*. These are pedagogical tools used to shape learning process, moral reasoning.

In addition, research draws from existing literature on Indian Knowledge Systems, indigenous pedagogy, educational philosophy and interpretations of Gita. The scope of study is primarily conceptual and theoretical. It does not attempt a verse-by-verse translation of Bhagavad Gita, rather it focuses on selected themes and pedagogical ideas that are central to education and learning. The paper seeks to contribute to contemporary academic discourse education and integrating culturally rooted knowledge systems in modern educational thought.

Conceptual Analysis

Educational Philosophy of Bhagavad Gita: Foundations of Indigenous Pedagogy

Bhagavad Gita articulates the educational philosophy that is deeply rooted in Indian Knowledge Systems. Education, as mentioned in Gita, is not just grasping knowledge but actually applying it in its concrete form. It is the acquisition of skills, learning their techniques, aiming at holistic development of individual. Some of key elements of education are:

- 1. Knowledge:** Knowledge is the vital element distinguishing a learned men from uneducated one. It stands as the central theme in learning centred model. As mentioned in Gita, Knowledge is not a single idea. It explains it in multiple forms, moving from worldly understanding to the highest spiritual wisdom. It is divided in 3 types, namely *Sattvic*, *Rajasic*, *Tamasic*. **Sattvic Knowledge** (Goodness) is clear, unified, and insightful. It sees the one spiritual reality (*atman*) within all human beings. This leads to peace, clarity, and spiritual development. This is the highest form of knowledge. **Rajasic Knowledge** (Passion) is analytical, driven by desire, ego, and self-interest. It views things as separate and distinct, often mistaking the worldly for the ultimate truth.

It creates ambition, attachment, and confusion, keeping one in the middle path of material existence. It is the middle form of knowledge. **Tamasic Knowledge** (Ignorance) is deluded, inverted, and lacking perspective. It mistakes a small part for the whole, calls evil good, and justifies delusion. It leads to darkness, laziness, stubbornness. This is the lowest form of knowledge. (Bhagavad Gita, Chapter 18)

“In this world, there is nothing as purifying as knowledge. One who has attained perfection in yoga finds this knowledge within himself in due course of time.” (Bhagavad Gita, 4.38)

This quote briefly explains how knowledge purifies the soul (atman) by eliminating ignorance, gloominess, doubts and hurdles. Purification is necessary in order to attain supreme wisdom. The only source of purification is balanced and true knowledge in order to move to the direction of spiritual development. It is not achieved at once, but with due course of time.

There are two types of knowledge, *apara vidya* and *para vidya*. Former is knowledge of the material world, rituals, sciences, and intellect. It provides a foundation, manage the material world, and build intellectual readiness for spiritual realisation. Latter is knowledge of the imperishable Brahman, the Supreme Self, the ultimate reality. It is to achieve liberation (moksha), direct experience of the Divine, going beyond the limitations of senses. Bhagavad Gita is itself a text of *para vidya* because it imparts direct knowledge of the Supreme Being.

- 2. Guru-Shishya relation:** In Bhagavad Gita, when Lord Krishna is preaching, he is acting as a teacher (*guru*) and Arjuna as disciple (*shishya*). It portrays a deep connection between a teacher and a student as when Arjuna got overwhelmed by emotions, Lord Krishna was there to guide him and remind of his *dharma* as a warrior. The respect and devotion to a teacher is *dharma* of a student. In ancient times, students used to reside at teacher’s place (*gurukul*) and away from parents so they could focus on studies. Guru used to teach students not only material knowledge but also the spiritual knowledge which was far from our senses. This is an important element of indigenous pedagogy embedded in Indian Knowledge Systems.

“Learn the truth by approaching a spiritual master. Inquire from him with reverence and render service unto him. Such an enlightened soul can impart knowledge unto you because he has seen the truth.” (Bhagavad Gita,4.34)

This verse clearly explains the importance of Guru in life of a student because a teacher is experienced in their field and he/she has seen and applied the knowledge in its concrete form.

- 3. Dialogic context (Samvada- based learning):** The entire Bhagavad Gita is written in dialogic form. In indigenous pedagogy, *samvada*- based learning has an important place because questioning things makes us understand them in a better way. Earlier, students used to follow dialogic method where teacher used to counter question students making them ponder over the question and look for possible outcomes. This method proved to be a better alternative as unless a student looks for answers themselves, there can’t be proper understanding.

4. **Karma Yoga:** Karma literally means action. In education process, action is required and is of utmost importance. Gita gives necessary importance to *karma yoga* (action). Learning process is not just confined to gaining knowledge but to put it to action. For example, a doctor learned all the methods of treatment but doesn't treat patients then what's the use of that knowledge. Proper action is required in order to fully comprehend a topic. Thus, action is required in the process of knowledge.

These were some of the main elements of Indigenous pedagogy embedded in Bhagavad Gita. Let's look at some examples of these principles into practice which will give us insights into how these can be applied.

Philosophy Into Practice

These principles of Indigenous Pedagogy mentioned in Bhagavad Gita is put to practice in the form of NEP 2020. Now what is NEP 2020? National Education Policy 2020 is a recent reform in education sector in India. This policy has sought to reform the pre-existing rigid model with a more flexible one focusing on learner and their comfort for pursuing education. Some of the key features of NEP 2020 are:

1. **Curriculum Reduction:** The reform states that it has removed burden on students by focusing on core essentials and removing extra subjects not necessary so that rote memorisation is replaced with critical thinking. It will make education process fun for students as they won't feel it like a burden.
2. **Learner-Centred:** This policy gave importance to learners by giving them flexibility in choosing their subjects with multiple entry and exit points focusing on learner's needs and requirements. This is a plus point as the earlier rigid system was making herd mentality with no flexibility and only focusing on making students a machine.
3. **Holistic Learning:** The new policy focuses on overall development of a student taking inspiration from Indigenous Pedagogy principles. Now, a learner can ensure their overall development as it introduced 360-degree holistic progress cards. This is a positive reform as the previous model was more teacher-centric than learner-centric. Focuses on experiential learning where a student learns through practical means.
4. **Mother Tongue Learning:** Now, the education process is to be in mother tongue of an individual. This will ensure cultural acceptance in students as they can stay close to their cultural roots and not be a victim of colonial legacy in order to get education. It will not make us colonial puppets and inculcate cultural proximity with a learner.
5. **Gita in Curriculum:** NEP ensures Gita is introduced in curriculum with an idea to make students aware of their ancient roots. It is not a religious text and is secular in nature guiding us to take decisive actions, teaching life skills, moral education required in practical world so that they don't get nervous when facing real-life problems.

These were some of the key features which takes inspiration from Gita.

Challenges in the Way

Implementing the policy tells us the problems that stand in the way which are to be solved. The key challenges are:

Gita has many terms which are metaphysical in nature which when are to be taught to school students makes it complicated to comprehend. These terms might make students puzzled and make it boring if not taught in an easy manner. This is one of the key challenges. Another challenge is Teacher Preparedness. Introducing new policies is not enough, they are to be implemented appropriately. There is a need to train teachers effectively so that they can preach the future generations with clarity. This is another important challenge in the way.

Curriculum and policy gaps is another hurdle. Introduction is not enough; there's a need to effectively implement the policies at ground level. In reality, only policies are introduced but ground reality is far different. Another is resource scarcity as policies state new smart classrooms are to be introduced but are they actually provided. In rural areas, we still don't have proper classrooms.

Education in ancient times was oral in nature but in this digital era, oral form of education is not acceptable. The circumstances change according to introduction of new ideas. Thus, this oral form of education is to be replaced with digital solution. These are some of the challenges that stand tall in the way.

Way Forward

In order to overcome these challenges, there is a need to come up with ideas to move forward. Firstly, we need to introduce Gita to students with easy and understandable language so that it gets simple for students to grasp. It could be done in animation form with *shlokas* recitation in background in lyrical theme. This is an easy and reformable idea.

Secondly, teacher training programs are to be started at a large scale in order to get the teachers updated with latest ideas to deal with technology and students in a better way. There is also a need to introduce institution training for effective implementation of policies without any chaos.

With policies, government need to provide adequate resources as well. The resources are to be given and reviewed timely. Digital resources are need of the time and be focused on. Thus, digital resources should be first priority.

These were some of the suggestions we can work on.

Conclusion

Gita and education are deeply interconnected. Indigenous pedagogy takes inspiration from Bhagavad Gita. These principles are a part of Indian Knowledge systems where karma yoga, knowledge, devotion stands as important elements. These principles are put to practice in form of NEP 2020. It brought reforms in the rigid system. With policies comes challenges which are discussed properly in the paper.

It also mentions suggestions which can be worked on. Thus, this paper focuses on through discussion on Gita, Education and Pedagogy.

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